

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-benzene Sulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part V. Effect of Substitution

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The acid dissociation constants of the complexing ligands *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzene sulphonyl glycines have been determined in 1:1 aqueous-ethanolic solution and pK^* values were found to be 4.40, 4.36 and 4.35 respectively. They form complex compounds with some divalent metal ions and behave as biprotic bidentate ligands. The stability constants of complex compounds formed by Cu (II), Zn (II) and Cd (II) with those reagents have also been determined in 1:1 aqueous-ethanolic solution and the results were evaluated graphically with the help of the projection strip method of Rossotti, Rossotti and Sillén.

The present communication seeks to study the effect of the introduction of a nitro-group in the benzene ring situated at the farthest end of the ligand molecule of N-benzene-sulphonylglycine and the position of the nitro-group in the benzene ring on the stabilities of the proton complexes and metal complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of the solutions and other experimental set up were the same as described in Part I of this series¹. The preparation and other properties of the ligands *o*-nitro-, *m*-nitro-, and *p*-nitrobenzene-sulphonylglycines abbreviated respectively as RoH_2 , R_mH_2 and R_pH_2 were reported in Part II². The titrations for the measurement of the stability constants were carried out everywhere in 1 : 1 aqueous-ethanol following the technique of Calvin and Wilson³.

For the evaluation of the (H^+) in this mixed-solvent from a knowledge of the pH-meter reading calibrated with an aqueous-buffer, the following direct method was employed. A 50 ml of 0.05M HNO_3 in 1 : 1 aqueous-ethanol solution was titrated with 0.51M+ KOH (also taken in the same solvent mixture) and the pH-values noted and from a plot of pH vs $\log (H^+)$ (Fig. 1), the (H^+) corresponding to any pH was extrapolated, assuming that the behaviour of the strong acids is the same in aqueous and mixed solvents.

The dissociation constants of the ligand acids i.e. the pK^* values were determined¹ by pH-titrations of a reagent solution of known concentration in 1 : 1 aqueous-ethanol with a standard KOH solution taken in the same solvent mixture. From these $\bar{n}_B$, the

1. Ghosh and Majumder, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 945.
2. Ghosh and Majumder, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 115.
3. Calvin and Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.

average number of acidic H attached per ligand molecule, was calculated using

$$\bar{n}_a = \frac{R - P}{R} \frac{H^+}{OH^-}$$

where R = total concentration of the reagent.
 P = total concentration of the alkali added.

FIG. 1

The plots of $\bar{n}_a$ vs pH are presented in the lowest curves of figures 3, 5, 7 and 9 for RH_2 , R_0H_2 , R_mH_2 and R_pH_2 . Whence pK^* values were found out as pH when $\bar{n}_a = \frac{1}{2}$. The pK values are recorded in table I.

The formation of complex compounds between RH_2 (the present type of ligands) and bivalent metal ions may be assumed to take place in successive stages.

The complex acids also dissociate in stages like

The following abbreviations have been used

The formation constants of the metal chelates have been determined at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ in 1 : 1 aqueous-ethanol, by titrating a mixture of the metal nitrate in presence of free HNO_3 ,

and the organic ligands with KOH solution also in the same solvent mixture. From the measured pH-values and from a knowledge of the concentrations of the pertinent species in solution, R and $\bar{n}f$ values were calculated using the following two equations:

FIG. 2

$$R_0 = R - (P + H - OH^- - F - M_I - 2M_{II})$$

where, R_0 = concentration of the free ligand,

F = concentration of the free mineral acid.

So long the complex formation takes place, M_I, M_{II}, OH^- are small.

Average number of ligands attached per metal ion

$$\bar{n}f = \frac{R - R_0 (1 + K^*/H^+)}{M}, \quad M = \text{total concentration of the metal ion.}$$

FIG. 3

The results are recorded graphically as the plots of $\bar{n}f$ against $p(b)$ ($=pH + \log R_0$) and their formation curves are shown in Figs. 2,4,6 and 8 at two different concentrations of the metal ions in most cases using ligands RH_2, R_0H, RmH_2 and R_pH_2 respectively, to show

that there was no polynuclear complex formation and the results were reproducible. The formation curves of the complexes of RH_n with the metal ions have been redrawn from previous data⁴ and grouped together with the others to have the comparisons more explicit and the values of the constants have been reevaluated.

FIG. 4

The correct values of pK_1 and pK_2 were found out graphically with the help of the projection strip method of Rossotti and Sillén⁵. Both the projection strip and the experimental plots were drawn on the same scale on a transparent paper and comparing the lower portion i.e. below $\alpha f=1$, of the experimental plots (vide discussion below) with the "projection-strip" theoretical plots, values of $p(K_1/K_2)$ and $p(K_1 \cdot K_2)$ were obtained from which individual pK_1 and pK_2 values were calculated.

The values of the successive stability constants $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ were calculated using the equations¹:

$$k_1 = \frac{K_1}{K^*} \text{ and } k_2 = \frac{K_2}{K^*}$$

The results are recorded in table II.

In the titrations for the determination of the stability constants the values of $\bar{n}_H$ for the complex acids $H_2 M^{++} R_2$ were calculated using the equations¹,

$$\bar{n}_H = 4 - \frac{(P + H^+ - F - OH^-) - R_1}{M}$$

$$\text{where } R_1 = \frac{R - 2M}{1 + \frac{H^+}{K^*}}$$

From the plots of pH vs $\bar{n}_H$, as shown in the Figs. 3, 5, 7 and 9, pK_1 and pK_2 were

4. Rossotti, and Rossotti and Sillén, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 203.

5. Rossotti and Rossotti: "The Determination of Stability constants", McGraw Hill Book Co., 1961.

evaluated by Bjerrum's half- $\bar{n}$ method which were then corrected using the following two equations :

FIG. 5

$$K_3 = (H^+) \bar{n}_{H=3/2} \left[1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{[H^+] \bar{n}_{H=3/2}}{3K_4}} \right]$$

$$K_4 = [H^+] \bar{n}_{H=1/2} \left[1 + \frac{3[H^+] \bar{n}_{H=1/2}}{K_3} \right]$$

The values are also recorded in Table II.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The NH₂-group being a nucleophilic one when introduced into the α-carbon atom of acetic acid should decrease its acidity still further and due to the formation of zwitter

FIG. 6

ion, the acidity is actually very small. When the strongly electron attracting benzene

sulphonyl group is introduced on the amino-group of glycine (i.e. RH_2) profound changes due to the inductometric effects take place and the NH -group becomes more acidic than basic. This inductive effect decreases rapidly as the distance from the source increases. The effect of substitution is considerable on the NH -group, but slight on the carboxyl-acidity (cf: Table I).

TABLE I

Acid	CH_3COOH	$\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$	RH_2	R_oH_2	R_mH_2	R_pH_2
pK^*	4.80	9.80	4.50	4.40	4.36	4.35

When a NO_2 -group is introduced into the benzene ring, the substituent on the N-atom becomes still more electronegative and the system of conjugated double bonds is extended in the case of R_oH_2 and R_pH_2 . The order of increasing carboxyl acidity is:

The NO_2 -group in the *o*-position, due to the H-bonding may form a ring which in its turn has a stabilising effect on the proton complex of the ligand.

On plotting $\bar{n}_f$ against $\text{p}(b)$, $\text{p}(b)$ being equal to $(\text{pH} + \log R_0)$ the formation curves are obtained of which the upper portion appear to be distorted when they are compared with the theoretical (normalised) curves, presumably due to the overlapping of the third

FIG. 7

step reaction with the second one i.e. due to the simultaneous formation of the bis-chelates and neutralisation of the enhanced imidoacidities over a certain pH -range.⁶ Therefore, the values of K_1 and K_2 calculated by the usual mathematical methods cannot be regarded as

6. Dutta and Rabin, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1956, 52, 1117.

correct because of this overlapping as well as of the errors inherent in the method when K_1 and K_2 are close. Therefore, the values obtained by the "projection strip" curve fitting method of Sillén and co-workers, assuming no distortion in the lower portion of the curve i.e. below $\bar{n}_f = 1$, appears to be more realistic.

FIG. 8

The ligands used RH_2 , R_0H_2 , R_mH_2 and R_pH_2 are closely similar differing only slightly in their basicities and in some steric effects. Any precise correlation of the stabilities of the metal chelates with the structure of the chelating agent is difficult, because they differ only slightly and due to the fact that they are studied under comparable but not rigorously identical conditions. Nevertheless, some general trends are noticeable. With Zn (II) and Cd (II), the overall stability constants are in the order with R_0H_2 and R_mH_2 : Zn(II) < Cd (II). But with R_pH_2 and RH_2 , the stability order is reversed i.e. Zn(II) > Cd(II). Obviously, this is because of the fact that a larger metal ion is needed in complexes of R_0H_2 and R_mH_2 to prevent the two ligands to interact with each other in their bis-chelates whereas a smaller metal ion fits rightly in the bis-chelates of RH_2 and R_pH_2 .

FIG. 9

Contrary to usual experiences, in the case of Cu(II)-chelates k_2 has been found to be greater than k_1 . This may be due to some new stabilising phenomena brought into play

with the formation of the *bis*-chelates and the enhancement of the imido-acidity. On the ionisation of the H-atom in the NH-group, the increase in the electron density on the N-atom is redistributed resulting in the strengthening of the bonds which is accompanied by color change from light blue to deep blue.

TABLE II

Metal ion	Initial conc.	Reagent	log k_1	log k_2	pK ₃	pK ₄
Cu ²⁺	0.01 M	RH ₂	2.40	2.80	4.19	7.70
		RoH ₂	2.20	3.20	4.33	7.00
		R _m H ₂	2.66	3.10	4.34	6.80
		R _φ H ₂	2.25	3.21	4.24	—
Zn ²⁺	0.01M	RH ₂	1.87	2.10	6.61	7.88
		RoH ₂	1.94	1.46	5.97	7.60
		R _m H ₂	2.18	1.46	5.83	7.21
		R _φ H ₂	2.23	1.79	5.82	7.06
Cd ²⁺	0.01M	RH ₂	1.71	2.21	7.28	8.89
		RoH ₂	2.14	1.46	6.57	8.57
		R _m H ₂	2.25	1.71	7.17	9.19
		R _φ H ₂	2.34	1.58	—	—

The imido-H becomes more acidic on the formation of a metal nitrogen coordinate bond

This acidity enhancement is quite significant in all the cases (vide Table II), but very marked in the cases of metals forming more stable chelates e.g., Cu (II) and Hg (II). The enhancement of acidity appears to be a function of the metal-nitrogen bond strength or approximately proportional to the stability of the metal chelates.